

PhenoMeNal

Deliverable 6.2

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Abstract: The PhenoMeNal VRE Portal is the entry point (gateway) to all the tools and workflows on offer. The Portal is available at http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal/	

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The PhenoMeNal VRE Portal is the entry point (Gateway) to all the tools and workflows on offer. The Portal is available at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal/>, and in the long term will enable users to deploy their own PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Environments on private and public cloud providers, as well as provide documentation for deployments on local hardware. Most of the tools are accessible through the Galaxy¹ workflow environment, and in the future through command line alternatives like Jupyter/iPython. All the tools in the workflow environment have been deployed as Docker containers, to fully modularise the architecture, and we also make them available as such. This deliverable describes the VRE Portal, UX design process and the general architecture of the portal.

During our recent UX testing, the users did not fully understand, nor trust, the term “Virtual” in VRE. So to make this more clear we have chosen to externally brand the portal as “*PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment Portal*”. This improved the trust issues we experienced in the first round of testing and apparently made more sense to test users. Further in this document, and internally in the project “VRE Portal” is used as the descriptive term.

2. CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The deliverable has contributed towards the following project objectives:

- D6.2 PhenoMeNal VRC (static) portal publicly available
- MS6.2 Initial release of PhenoMeNal VRC portal online

3. DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

In this deliverable we are describing the first version of the VRE Portal, available at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal/>. The VRE Portal will be the first entry point for the users to interact with PhenoMeNal, showcasing its capabilities, displaying the available analysis tools and allowing the users to automatically deploy the PhenoMeNal VRE infrastructure to cloud providers of their choice. The main user platforms for the deployed VRE infrastructure will be a customised build of the Galaxy workflow and the Jupiter/iPython notebook systems, ensuring these environments will scale to meet the computational needs. A first example of these builds is our public PhenoMeNal Workflow instance, available at <http://public.phenomenal-h2020.eu/>. This deliverable is not focused on contextual deployment of the VRE infrastructures, but on the web portal that will allow those VRE infrastructures to be deployed.

¹ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

3.1. Usability Testing Methodology and Design

Guidelines

This section outlines design guidelines for the “PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Environment Portal” (VRE Portal) and the UX methodology that resulted in this prototype. We hired the same UX expert we used for the first UX workshop; see **D6.1 User Experience Document on VRC Design Guide** for more information.

UX Methodology

The following plan was developed to ensure a user centric design of the PhenoMeNal VRE portal.

Test Period	Description
Period 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Stakeholder requirement identification.● Heuristic Analysis of stakeholder wireframes.● Identification and recruitment of participants.● Moderator guide developed for usability testing.● First prototype version designed (0.1).
Period 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Round 1 of usability testing with 4 participants.● Reporting and review of usability testing results.● Redesign of a new prototype version (0.2)● Interview of a clinician.● Recruitment of participants for round 2.
Period 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Round 2 of usability testing with 4 participants.● Reporting and review of usability testing results.● Redesign of final version of prototype version (0.3).● Final version and annotations.

Usability Testing

Number of participants

In total we had tested 8 different participants over two rounds of usability tests. This is more than sufficient to gather valuable insight into our design. According to UX experts², 80% of usability problems can be found with approximately 5 participants. Adding more participants does not necessarily detect many more issues and the cost/benefit ratio quickly decreases. This publication³ outlines the model used to determine the optimal cost/benefit ratio on the number of users to test.

Test panel - 4 participants per round

As we work in an Agile⁴ iterative process we were able to quickly highlight key issues with the first round of testing and iteratively redesign for the second round. It was clear from the first round that we had some fundamental issues in terms of the user's understanding of the project which had to be rectified before going any further.

According to Nielsen: "The last point also explains why the true answer to "how many users" can sometimes be much smaller than 5. If you have an Agile-style UX process⁵ with very low overhead, your investment in each study is so trivial that the cost–benefit ratio is optimized by a smaller benefit. For really low-overhead projects, it's often optimal to test as little as 2 users per study. For some other projects, 8 users — or sometimes even more — might be better. For most projects, however, you should stay with the tried-and-true: 5 users per usability test."

Participant Recruitment

Participants were recruited based on our persona profile developed during the first PhenoMeNal UX workshop (D6.1). None of the participants were project partners and they had no previous knowledge of the PhenoMeNal project.

Clinician Interviews

It was rather difficult to get time scheduled with clinicians, we were unable to expand on this. We interviewed one clinician in round 1 using the Clinician Moderator Guide (Appendix 7.1). Furthermore we knew that a clinician would be unlikely to be the person who will create the VRE and this is more likely to be the bioinformatician. However, we need to keep in mind the needs of clinical metabolomics in general and hence it is recommended that as the project develops we work closely with clinician collaborators.

Based on one interview we found the following:

² [How Many Test Users in a Usability Study? - Nielsen Norman Group](#)

³ <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=169166>

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agile_management

⁵ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/agile-user-experience-projects/>

- There is a massive skills gap when it comes down to the processing analysis and experimental setup of a Metabolomics experiment, which needs to be overcome so that clinicians can make sense of their data.
- Bioinformaticians coming into the field need more guidance to help them get started and make the analysis reproducible.
- Even for Bioinformaticians, many cloud concepts were foreign or they were rarely familiarised with them (for instance, authentication procedures or appliances deployment ideas).

Usability Testing Results

We conducted two rounds of usability testing each with 4 participants remotely. For each round we had different participants, no participant was involved more than once. A moderator guide was written for each round so that the test would be conducted in exactly the same way and to reduce any confounding variables.

1. Moderator Guide Round 1 (Appendix 7.2)
2. Moderator Guide Round 2 (Appendix 7.3)

Participants (*Personas; Bioinformaticians and Clinicians*) were asked permission to screen record the test. All videos are available internally to the consortium with restricted permissions for confidentiality reasons. Videos should not be identifiable.

Here we give a brief description of our findings for each round and how they have informed the VRE Portal design.

Key Findings of Round 1 (Wireframe version 0.1)

The first round of testing produced the most amount of issues. Below we report what were regarded as critical issues and derive design recommendations for mitigation.

No.	Finding (Issue)	Design Recommendation (Mitigation)
1	The home page and VRE Portal did not properly communicate what the portal was offering. Many participants had a limited understanding of what a “virtual research environment” meant.	Changed the name of the portal to “Cloud Research Environment”. Redesign the Home and VRE Portal pages to explain what the product was.
2	The participants had significant trust issues with the website. They did not recognise PhenoMeNal as a brand/project and were not keen on parting with their personal account details for their own cloud provider.	Made the PhenoMeNal project partner’s logos more apparent, including the EU logo. We made clear who was hosting the PhenoMeNal cloud and also ensured that users understood that we did not store the cloud provider login details.
3	The VRE setup process was too complicated. Many participants complained and said they would drop out of the setup process.	We reduced complexity, asked less questions and reverted to simple defaults.
4	The amount of choice in Cloud providers made it confusing.	Placed more importance on the default PhenoMeNal Cloud as a provider and make participants aware that internal clouds behind the clinic-firewall are an option where ELSI are concerned.
5	The relationship between the applications in the “App Hub” and the VRE were not clear. Many users were confounded by this.	Renamed the “App Hub” to “App Library” and we also added information explaining the relationship. We highlighted the fact that all access to the apps were through Jupyter and Galaxy.

Key Findings of Round 2 (Wireframe version 0.2)

The second round of testing went far better. Participants, none of them involved in round 1, now did not have any trust issues with the site and could easily complete the setup process of the VRE without any major problems.

No.	Finding (Issue)	Design Recommendation (Mitigation)
1	The homepage was still a bit too overwhelming. Participants were not sure where to focus their attention.	Reduced the text on the home page. Made the CTA (call to action) buttons a lot clearer and the essence of the home page a bit more streamlined.
2	Half the participants were able to understand the architecture of the VRE and how it was setup. More work needed to explain it to other half.	The VRE pages were redesigned with a carousel explaining how it was all hooked up.
3	The VRE pages were too similar to the PhenoMeNal home page and confused the navigation.	The VRE pages were redesigned to ensure a clear differentiation with the home page.

Design Guidelines

Responsive Design

The desktop screen resolution that was used in the wireframes were the recommended standard based on worldwide usage: 1368 px (Width) x 768 px (Height). Please note that this resolutions was only used for the wireframe testing.

We have devised the site to be designed Responsively⁶ and additional mobile and tablet resolutions be selected. We have chosen to use Google AngularJS 2⁷ with Material Design⁸. Figure 3.1 shows how the home page looks on a smartphone screen. This Responsive layout is enabled without any further software development.

The Google AngularJS 2 framework is one of the most cutting-edge web development technologies. It is a JavaScript-based open-source client and server-side web application framework mainly maintained by Google and by a community of individuals and corporations to address many of the challenges encountered in developing single-page applications. The reasons for using this AngularJS 2 framework were its ease of development, mobile driven, better

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Responsive_web_design

⁷ <https://angular.io/>

⁸ <https://material.google.com/>

performance, and easy applicability, together with the support of modern browsers. In addition to that, Material Design makes more liberal use of grid-based layouts, responsive animations and transitions, padding, and depth effects such as lighting and shadows. We take advantage of using Material Design for making the VRE Portal look professional, trustworthy and cleanly laid out.

The following guidelines should be adhered to in order to ensure that it remains a responsive site.

- I. Buttons and actions should be clear and should not rely on tooltips. On mobile the user does not have access to tooltips so ensure that everything is labelled and the correct icons are used for buttons.
- II. The minimum recommended button size for mobile is 36px x 36px. Stay close to these guidelines to ensure every user can tap on every button. Obviously if the button is rectangular then this could be reduced in height for example if the width is increased eg. 46px x 32 px.
- III. All imagery introduced should be scalable for smaller screen sizes.
- IV. Make the site accessible⁹ which improves readability and responsivity overall.

Typography

EMBL-EBI underwent a complete redesign of all websites in 2014. It was natural to use our extensive experience from this project and take inspiration from this work. The minimum recommended font sizes are based on the EMBL-EBI style guidelines¹⁰ and we follow the guidelines: *“Body text will be set in Verdana, which provides optimum readability across a wide range of operating systems and devices. Headings use Helvetica Neue (defaulting to Helvetica). Base font size for body text is 13px with a line height of 20px. Across the site, text is sized using percentages.”*

As we use mainly two types of headers i.e. the main heading of the page and embedded headers within the page which maybe strap lines like on the home page.

Type	Font size recommendation	%
Normal	13px	100
Header 1 (Main title pages)	36 px	277
Header 2 (Subheadings)	24 px	182

⁹ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/web/style/accessibility>

¹⁰ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/web/style/typography>

3.2. Wireframes

To ensure we can rapidly prototype and change our design, we chose to implement the UX prototypes as low-fidelity wireframe mockups. The wireframes are simple sketch style pages, that have some URLs/links that are clickable and will take the developer to the next page.

The final wireframes for our design are version 0.3 (Appendix 7.4) and below (Figures 1 & 2) are a couple of examples from our testing, out of a total of 29 wireframes designed and to be translated into real pages. The final wireframe version 0.3 is the result of the UX process through the two rounds of user testing described before.

Figure 1. Wireframe mockup of the PhenoMeNal Application Library (App Library), showing the VMs and tools that are available in the VRE, branded as Cloud Research Environment (CRE). The user can interact with the App Library through a search field (upper middle-right), through category selectors (Metabolomics technology and Data analysis stage; middle left) and can influence the sorting and layout of the shown applications (upper right). Clicking on an App takes the user to an

individual page for that App with further details and instructions. The App Library in general was well received by users in the tests, as it is a concept to which many users can relate to.

Figure 2. Wireframe mock-up of the VRE Portal homepage. Note the line that reads “fold” is where the screen would initially end and the user will scroll down to see the rest. The home page essentially presents users with the ability to: (upper fold, left) Test-drive a public VRE deployment,

(upper fold, right) initiate the process to deploy their own VRE to a cloud provider, (second fold) browse the App DB, (third fold) understand from where the user would use the tools and finally (lower fold) learn about the hosts that support a public VRE.

3.3. VRE Portal Web Pages

This sections shows the initial real HTML pages of the static VRE Portal, derived from the mockup wireframes v0.3, and build as specified with AngularJS, Material Design and the design guidelines previously mentioned. Icons and figures were commissioned to the EMBL-EBI's Graphical Design Team through an iterative process involving PhenoMeNal developers, to convey the adequate ideas that each illustration had to convey (as defined in the UX process). This initial, partly static version, is currently accessible at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal>.

Landing page

In the landing page, the VRE Portal aims to engage the user with the main elements that the consortium wants to provide. Figure 3.1 & Figure 3.2 shows the landing page of the VRE Portal, from where the user can:

- Reach the test-drive (public instance) version of PhenoMeNal VRE: Currently a test-drive for the PhenoMeNal Galaxy instance running on top of a container orchestrator cluster, including PhenoMeNal tools, is available through the links. We expect to provide access to a Jupyter/iPython test-drive in the near future.
- Create a Cloud Research Environment (the public name chosen for VRE after UX sessions): Currently this leads to sample pages that show how the user will actually interact with the VRE Portal to trigger a deployment. This will be soon connected with our MANTL immutable image deployment through terraform and ansible produced by WP5. Triggering this process currently takes the user to the first deployment page (Figure 4) where the user is given more information about the process, certain concepts reaffirmed and presented with the main alternatives (cloud deployment or local deployment)
- Browse the App Library: Leads the user to a catalogue of tools (shown in Figure 7), in the form of Docker containers, that PhenoMeNal makes available through the deployed VREs. It also exposes the infrastructure Virtual Machines (VMs), made available as Virtual Machine Images (VMI). The App Library currently retrieves metadata for tools from the EGI AppDB.
- Get familiar with the products that PhenoMeNal can provide to them.

PhenoMeNa Gateway
Cloud Research Environment Portal

Home Cloud Research Environment App Library

Home

All libraries in the App Library run within the Cloud Research Environment on the cloud. This simplifies running and maintaining applications.

Access to the Virtual Research Environment is through Open Source scientific web environments such as Galaxy Workflow or Jupyter IPython coding web environment.

Test drive our Cloud Research Environment

[Galaxy Workflow](#) or [Jupyter IPython](#)

Note that this is a public instance accessible by everyone

An easy to use, cloud based scalable software infrastructure for metabolomic research

Want to give it a go?

[Create Cloud Research Environment](#)

[Find out more](#)

The open-source App Library provides a catalogue of free Metabolomic data analysis libraries available within the Cloud Research Environment

With user feedback and ratings it is easier to choose the best software for your analysis

[Browse App Library](#)

Access your Cloud Research Environment through standard scientific open-source web environments, Galaxy Workflow tool and Jupyter coding environment

With world leading e-Infrastructure partners your Cloud Research Environment is in safe hands

Our focus on clinical metabolomics ensures we take the utmost care in securing your environment and data

The Cloud Research Environment adheres to the strictest security measures. At no point do we store any information related to your own cloud provider

PhenoMeNa Cloud Hosts

Figure 3.1. PhenoMeNa VRE Portal home page. This is the initial static version, based on the v0.3 mockup wireframes, written with AngularJS and Material Design, and following the design guidelines outlined. As of this writing, the “Galaxy Workflow” button (Test drive section) leads to the PhenoMeNa Public Galaxy instance, and the “Browse App Library” button conducts the browser to a prototype version of the App Library which retrieves tools metadata from the EGI¹¹ Application Database¹² (AppDB). Currently, the “Create Cloud Research Environment” button (top right) takes

¹¹ <https://www.egi.eu/>

¹² <https://appdb.egi.eu/>

the user to a set of pages that in the future will provide the way to deploy a PhenoMeNal VRE to cloud providers.

PhenoMeNal Gateway
Cloud Research Environment Portal

Home

All libraries in the App Library run within the Cloud Research Environment on the cloud. This simplifies running and maintaining applications.

Access to the Virtual Research Environment is through Open Source scientific web environments such as Galaxy Workflow or Jupyter IPython coding web environment.

Test drive our Cloud Research Environment

Galaxy Workflow or Jupyter IPython

Note that this is a public instance accessible by everyone

An easy to use, cloud based scalable software infrastructure for metabolomic research

Want to give it a go?

Create Cloud Research Environment

Figure 3.2. PhenoMeNal VRE Portal home page when using a smaller screen. This illustrates how the Responsive design ensures a natural flow of all page elements.

Deployment pages

When the user chooses to create a Cloud Research Environment from the landing page (Figure 3.1), he/she is first presented with a page (Figure 4, which is the page corresponding to the wireframe shown in Figure 2) where two main alternatives are given: whether to deploy to a Cloud provider or to run the infrastructure on local hardware. Considering that the user might still be unconvinced by the prospect of cloud deployment, as it will in many cases lead to a direct monetary expense and it might not be yet clear what could be done with such deployment, the test-drive option is shown close by. This allows users to try a VRE that is similar to what could be deployed to cloud providers.

Cloud deployment pages

For users that are convinced that a cloud deployment is the way to proceed, the “Create Cloud Research Environment” button (Figure 4) will this time take them to the necessary steps to deploy the PhenoMeNal MANTL-based immutable images to a cloud provider for which they have credentials:

1. Sign-in (if the user has not already): The user is asked to sign-in through an identity provider (Google, LinkedIn, ORCID, ELIXIR, etc).
2. Choose Cloud provider: The user is asked to choose where it wants to deploy its VRE from the available cloud providers, giving PhenoMeNal Cloud Hosting as initial default. At this point, other providers are hidden for the least experienced user. More advanced users that have credentials for other cloud providers are expected to click on “Show all Cloud providers” link (Wireframes, Page 56, Appendix 7.4) below the default to show all the existing alternatives.
 - a. The list of alternative cloud providers will change in time as we are able to support deployment on them. We currently support OpenStack and we expect to support Google GCE and Amazon AWS in the short term. Support for the EGI Federated Cloud should come in the mid-term.
3. Verify credentials: to make sure that the user can deploy to the chosen provider, the deployment page asks the user to check its credentials against the chosen cloud provider. These credentials are used to run the deployment in the following steps. An example can be seen on Page 67 of Appendix 7.4.
4. Select hardware specs: Using metadata provided by the cloud providers, this deployment page will present available choices for Virtual Machines hardware specifications (how much hard drive, number of cores, GBs of RAM, etc). Since this impacts directly on the billing (Amazon, Google, privately paid cloud providers) or overall usage quota of the user (OpenStack, EGI, PhenoMeNal), this choice is left to the user. An example can be seen on Page 72, Appendix 7.4.
5. Wait for the deployment to take place: This is a process that should take a few minutes, and it is the required time to upload the infrastructure (MANTL) VMIs to the cloud provider of choice, spin up the instances, and configure any necessary live settings that cannot be set before runtime in the immutable images (ie. networking, access to shared file system, etc.). This time will vary from provider to provider. The user will be shown a progress bar of the process, as shown on Page 76, Appendix 7.4. The underlying process taking place here is the one defined by WP5.
6. Access to the deployed VRE: the user is presented with a page, like the one shown on the wireframes on Page 78 of Appendix 7.4, with links to access the different entry points

(Galaxy Workflow, Jupyter iPython, etc.) of its newly deployed VRE on the desired cloud provider. Clicking on these links, the user can start to do real work on the deployed VRE.

We are currently working on finishing the automatic cloud deployment interfaces and test the functionality, and we expect to be able to have a live version of this running on the portal in a few more months.

Cloud Research Environment

How does it work?

You follow our easy setup process and install the Cloud Research Environment (CRE) on the PhenoMeNal cloud or you can use your own cloud provider such as Amazon Cloud, Google Cloud etc.

● ○ ○ ○

All your favourite metabolomics analysis applications under one hood accessible through Open Source scientific web environments, Galaxy Workflow and Jupyter IPython coding environment

Test drive our Cloud Research Environment

Galaxy Workflow

or

Jupyter IPython

Note that this is a public instance accessible by everyone

Want to give it a go?

Create
Cloud Research Environment

Do you like the idea but need a local installation of the CRE?

Don't worry, we have a solution for you too. We can provide you with all the kit for a local installation of our Cloud Research Environment. This approach is more work for you but you will have the benefit of having all the apps on our App Library available locally.

Find out more about
local installation

You can install all the applications in our App Library locally.

You can install the whole Cloud Research Environment including our App Library locally.

PhenoMeNal Google Cloud Platform

EGI openstack amazon web services

Access to all the standard Cloud providers or own free PhenoMeNal cloud

Don't know much about Cloud providers but want to use our CRE? Don't worry. Our default setup process is easy to use and will get you started in no time

Figure 4. PhenoMeNal VRE Portal initial deployment page, where the user can choose from a Cloud deployment (upper fold) or installation on local hardware (middle fold). For the unconvinced user, the page presents a link to the test-drive installation (upper fold), to improve the understanding of what could be possible with a deployed VRE for the user.

Local deployment pages

In many scenarios, users won't have the ability or resources to deploy to a cloud provider, but might still be interested in using the PhenoMeNal infrastructure within local machines. This complicates automatic deployment as the normal path (cloud authentication, VMs provisioning, container orchestrator cluster setup, user frameworks deployment) cannot be followed in the same manner. When clicking on the button "Find out more about local installation" on the main deployment page (Figure 4), the user is taken to a page (Figure 5, local deployment page) with more information about the local installation, from where this process can be triggered. This again was suggested by the UX specialist as it seemed from the user sessions that many of this concepts had to be explained with more details for users to feel at ease to trigger them.

Cloud Research Environment / Local Installation

Your local installation of the CRE can be run as virtual machines or if you have administration rights directly on the computers

[Install your local Cloud Research Environment](#)

What will I need to run a local installation of the CRE?

Not much is the easy answer and we can guide you through it step-by-step

This solution specifically caters for clinical metabolomics where local installations are driven by the demands of the hospital IT requirements.

Local installations still benefit from all the applications in the App Library but are run on your local network.

A local installation of our CRE is ideal if you need to keep your data locally due to privacy and security

Figure 5. PhenoMeNal VRE Portal page for local installation of the PhenoMeNal VRE. This page allows the user to interact with a questionnaire (Figure 6) which will lead, according to previous

answers, to a set of documentation pages and tutorials to follow, to be able to run the PhenoMeNal installation locally.

Local deployment of the infrastructure will vary greatly according to the machine's specs (OS, administrative access, single/multiple machines, etc.) and intended aim of use (testing of the infrastructure, production usage). For this, together with the UX specialist, we have devised a tree-structured set of questions for the user about the local deployment, which, based on user's answers, will lead to different sets of documentation pages with instructions and VMIs/containers to download. Figure 6 illustrates such set of questions on the HTML pages, which were based on the wireframe shown in Page 18 of the Appendix 7.4. This page is reached by the user upon clicking on the button "Install your local Cloud Research Environment" on the local deployment page shown by Figure 5.

In order to direct you to the correct installation we need to ask you a few simple questions.

How many computer(s) do you want to run your analysis on?

Just on my
laptop or
desktop

On a cluster of
computers
(more than one)

What Linux operating system are you running on your computer(s)?

Ubuntu

Apple -
Minimum
supported
version 10.6+

I don't know

What sort of administration rights do you have over these computer(s)?

I do not have
installation
privilege on the
computer(s).

I have full
installation
privileges on
this computer(s).

I don't know

Thank you!

Based on your answers we have a set of instructions which will guide you through the installation process.

Click the button below to access your installation instructions.

Figure 6. PhenoMeNal local installation instruction page. Here we show how a user will navigate through the documentation using a decision tree style structure. In this example the user want to install the VRE on a locally (1st row) Apple computer (2nd row), where he/she has privileges to install software (3rd row). In the current version this will take the user the correct documentation on our Wiki pages.

Application Library

The Application Library (App Library) contains an overview of all the VMIs and tools contained within the PhenoMeNal VRE. VMIs are uploaded to our subgroup (PhenoMeNal under Elixir organisation) in the EGI AppDB and information are downloaded and parsed on dynamically. These VMIs can also be downloaded directly from the EGI AppDB, not only from our App Library. Each tool contained within the VMIs are also catalogued and described within the App Library. The tools are already available in the VRE and the detailed description is parsed from our GitHub organisation¹³.

Clicking on the “Browse App Library” on the landing page, takes the user to the main App Library page shown by Figure 7. On that page, the user can either browse, search or filter the catalogue Apps that will find available when deploying a VRE or trying the test-drive VRE. The search box to the upper right will, in a future release, dynamically display results as the user types and the filtering to the left can be used to narrow down tools by metabolomics technology or by the major step within the data analysis process. All of these functionalities are in operation.

App Library

App Library showcases all applications that are available via Galaxy workflows and Jupyter libraries through the Cloud Research Environment.

Search for Apps **Go**

Metabolomic Technology ⓘ

- DAD
- DIMS
- GC-MS
- LC-MS
- NMR
- RAMAN

Data analysis ⓘ

- Annotation
- Normalisation
- Processing
- Statistical Analysis

BATMAN NMR
Docker container produced by PhenoMeNal H2020 consortium for BATMAN NMR

PhenoMeNal MANTL
PhenoMeNal MANTL

W4M biosigner
Discovery of significant signatures from omics data

Figure 7. PhenoMeNal VRE App Library. This page is automatically populated with data from our VMs in our sub group on EGI AppDB. As we add more VMIs to EGI AppDB, this overview will dynamically grow.

¹³ <https://github.com/phnmnl>

Figure 7 does not reflect yet the complete availability of tools Dockerized and made available through the PhenoMeNal Galaxy installation, which should be all displayed in the App Library. This will be completed once we have defined all the elements of metadata that we want to expose for the tools, and from where all of these will be retrieved (EGI AppDB, GitHub repositories, PhenoMeNal Jenkins CI, PhenoMeNal Docker registry or other internal metadata stores).

Figure 8 shows the page presented to the user when clicking on a particular tool in the page of Figure 7, in this particular example, the BATMAN NMR tool. The tool page presents a description of the tool, usage instructions to be able to use the tool in isolation locally through its docker container, and links to its publication(s) and version control repository. In the near future, these type of pages will be completed to reflect all the elements agreed in the wireframe for the tools page (Page 32 in Appendix 7.4). We intend to improve shortly as well the usage instructions, not only to include advanced Docker usage, but to illustrate to users how to access the tool within the PhenoMeNal Galaxy and PhenoMeNal iPython/Jupyter frameworks. All of the tool pages (or App Pages) equivalent to Figure 8 shown at the currently available portal (<http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal/>) are dynamically populated, none of them are static HTML pages.

PhenoMeNal Gateway
Cloud Research Environment Portal

Home Cloud Research Environment App Library

App Library / BATMAN NMR

BATMAN NMR

Docker container produced by PhenoMeNal H2020 consortium for BATMAN NMR

Description BATMAN is an R package for estimating metabolite concentrations from Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectral data using a specialised MCMC algorithm. It deconvolutes peaks from 1-dimensional NMR spectra, automatically assigns them to specific metabolites from a target list and obtains concentration estimates. The Bayesian model incorporates information on characteristic peak patterns of metabolites and is able to account for shifts in the position of peaks commonly seen in NMR spectra of biological samples. It applies a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm to sample from a joint posterior distribution of the model parameters and obtains concentration estimates with reduced error compared with conventional numerical integration and comparable to manual deconvolution by experienced spectroscopists.

Usage Instruction To be able to use this container, you can either pull it and run it, or simply run it.

- Pull:

```
dock pull docker-registry.phenomenal-h2020.eu/phnmnl/batman
```

- Run:

```
dock run docker-registry.phenomenal-h2020.eu/phnmnl/batman
```

Publication Hao J., Liebeke M., Astle W., De Iorio M., Bundy J. G. & Ebbels T. M., *Bayesian deconvolution and quantification of metabolites in complex 1D NMR spectra using BATMAN*, *Nature Protocols*, 9, 1416-1427 (2014).

Github Repository <https://github.com/phnmnl/docker-batman>

Figure 8. PhenoMeNal VRE App Library details page (placeholder). This page is automatically generated using our VMI detail pages in EGI AppDB and PhenoMeNal GitHub repository pages for each tool. This type of page currently does not contain all of the elements that the UX process

committed to, as we are in the process of finding the best way to store all those different metadata parts, and how to access them.

Test-drive VRE workflow environment-PhenoMeNaL Galaxy deployment

The first version of the VRE, deployed as a *test-drive*, comprise of a set of metabolomics tools available through the Galaxy workflow environment. This instance runs as a container inside a Kubernetes cluster provisioned within the EMBL-EBI EMBASSY Cloud (OpenStack), and currently includes a small number of tools, which will be expanded as more tools are dockerized and “galaxified”. Currently, the PhenoMeNaL Galaxy deployment has tools for Fluxomics, an NMR tool, some tools from Workflow for Metabolomics (W4M) and RAW data conversion tools (for NMR and MS). Further details about the PhenoMeNaL Galaxy deployment can be found in Deliverable 5.2. This test drive instance is currently reachable when clicking on the button “Galaxy Workflow” on the page shown by Figure 4. We expect to have the iPython/Jupyter test-drive active soon.

The [PhenoMeNaL](#) Galaxy installation allows users to access all of the PhenoMeNaL containerised tools through a workflow environment, on an scalable infrastructure that can be deployed to public and private cloud installations.

This [PhenoMeNaL H2020](#) Galaxy instance, and all of its tools, run as containers on top of [Kubernetes](#), an open source container orchestrator system backed by Google. If you wish to deploy the [PhenoMeNaL Galaxy installation](#) on top of your own Kubernetes instance, you can find instructions at our [wiki](#).

The [PhenoMeNaL consortium](#) is driven by 14 European research groups with strong experience in the development of tools and methods for large data acquisition, integration and analysis for metabolic phenotypes, genome and cross-omics data.

PhenoMeNaL is funded by European Commission's Horizon2020 programme, grant agreement number 654241. The [Galaxy Project](#) is supported in part by [NHGRI](#), [NSF](#), [The Huck Institutes of the Life Sciences](#), [The Institute for CyberScience at Penn State](#), and [Johns Hopkins University](#).

Figure 9. PhenoMeNaL VRE Galaxy interface, with examples of newly integrated tools for Fluxomics, NMR and RAW formats converters at the left side-bar, under the “PhenoMeNaL H2020 Tools” section.

3.4. VRE Portal Technical Architecture

PhenoMeNal is very closely working with both Elixir¹⁴ and EGI. As part of this collaboration EMBL-EBI is in the process of finalising a new Authentication, Authorization and Profile (AAP) service. This will eventually give our users the ability to create a common identity for these 3 organisations. PhenoMeNal project members are currently testing some of the AAP features. All of PhenoMeNal VMIs will be available through the EGI AppDB. Further on this collaboration, PhenoMeNal has decided to create a sub-group (category) belonging to the Elixir virtual organisation (VO) under EGI AppDB. This ensures closer collaboration with Elixir and EGI, as well as the ability to share some common code base. In this version of the VRE and VRE Portal, PhenoMeNal distribute all VMIs under the appropriate VO and information is dynamically pulled back to the VRE Portals App Library. In the App Library metadata information from both the EGI VO and the PhenoMeNal GitHub repositories is combined into concise views for each VMI and relevant tool.

PhenoMeNal has created repositories in GitHub for all tools and VM development. All tools and applications are tested and built upon every git commit using a Jenkins¹⁵ continuous integration server (CI).

In terms of automatic deployment of VRE to cloud providers, the VRE Portal will leverage work developed in collaboration with the EMBL-EBI Cloud team. This collaboration include cloud access (OpenStack, Amazon AWS, Google GCE) and deployment (Terraform and Ansible codified infrastructure-as-code) with a web frontend written in AngularJS 2. This is the same web framework used for the PhenoMeNal VRE Portal, so the integration is virtually seamless. Prototypes of this deployment interface are already operational and the EMBL-EBI Cloud team uses them for some applications. Once we finalise the detailed deployment scripts in WP5 (which also utilise terraform and ansible to deploy MANTL), these will be integrated in the VRE Portal, in addition to any necessary additions. This will enable the automatic cloud deployment process at the VRE Portal.

In future releases of the VRE and VRE Portal we will integrate with the EGI Federated Cloud¹⁶ for full feature integration, including VMcaster and VMcatcher capabilities. (VMcatcher is listening and subscribing to an virtual image list. VMcaster is the announcer)

From the VRE Portal the user will have the ability to test-drive an existing VRE, deploy the VRE to commercial cloud providers or the EGI Federated Cloud grid. In addition the VRE, in form of a VMI can be downloaded and deployed to local servers to comply with local Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI).

¹⁴ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/>

¹⁵ <https://jenkins.io/>

¹⁶ <https://www.egi.eu/infrastructure/cloud/>

Figure 10. An overview of main current and proposed components. All software developments, including Dockerfiles, are stored in our GitHub repositories. We add pages with metadata for our VMs and tools in EGI AppDB as part of the PhenoMeNal sub-group of Elixir. On the VRE Portal we dynamically combine the information from GitHub (Tools and Applications) and EGI AppDB (Appliances/VMs), thus avoiding duplication of information. Please note that at the time of writing, the PhenoMeNal OpenStack is not available as part of the EGI Federated Cloud.

4. WORK PLAN

4.1. Structure and management of WP6 Tasks

As for the rest of the project all WP6 activities has been managed and tracked using our Pivotal Tracker project, regular online and face-to-face meetings has also been conducted. For certain technical components the EMBL-EBI PhenoMeNal team has been working together with EMBL-EBI Elixir teams on a new Authentication, Authorisation and Profile (Single Sign-On) Service. In the future this will give users the opportunity to create a local PhenoMeNal account and/or a global combined PhenoMeNal, Elixir, EGI and EMBL-EBI account.

Utilisation of resources

The total PMs (person months) utilised in WP6 until M12 (inclusive):

Partners	EMBL-EBI	IPB	ICL	UB	CRIMMP	UOXF	UU	CEA
PMs	12	1	3	1	0.5	4	1.7	3

5. DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The delivery is delayed: No

6. CONCLUSION

Through our iterative usability testing and low fidelity mock-ups we were able to design a VRE Portal that suits the community. This first release already includes dynamically parsed information from both GitHub and EGI AppDB for the App Library, live access to a functional test-drive VRE with the PhenoMeNal Galaxy installation, and access to real documentation through the decision-tree for local deployment. These attributes take the initial version of the VRE Portal beyond a mere static version, exceeding the functionality promised at this stage in the initial work plan. We will continue to develop the VRE Portal using the same UX principles applied so far. The Portal will be extensively expanded over the following year.

The VRE Portal has been implemented with modern web technologies and design guidelines to provide the best user experience and maximize the ability of the user to accomplish the required tasks. The website is responsive to different browsing setups (mobile, tablet, desktop) to make sure that the user can access the portal from a variety of devices.

The UX exercise of exposing the VRE Portal wireframes to real users revealed key concerns and trust issues that otherwise would have only surfaced when the system went into real usage, potentially losing users then. Cloud technologies and their usage is still something foreign for most scientific computing users, and as such the VRE Portal needs to accommodate for this if we want to maximize the number of user that can successfully use the PhenoMeNal infrastructure. Every effort to do this has been done in the VRE Portal design.

7. APPENDIX

7.1. Clinician Moderator Guide

Aim: We want to understand what triggers a decision to use a metabolomics pipeline for a clinician. How do they discover these methods? We are assuming that a bioinformatician will install the app and get it running but before that happens they might get a request from a clinician.

Introduction

Hi and thank you for your time? We are developing a virtual research metabolomics environment to make Metabolomics accessible to clinicians such as yourself. In order to ensure it is fit for purpose we would like to ask you a few questions. In particular we are interested in understanding how you go about discovering new methods, what information you require and what are the key factors in determining whether to try out a new technology.

I would like to record this conversation so that I can do later analysis. No personal details will be stored and the results of this interview will be anonymised. For example, you will be referred to as Participant 1. The interview won't take more than 30 minutes.

Questions

Work related

1. Can you tell me your job title and a little about your work?
2. How have you been using metabolomics research as a clinician? What type of questions are you trying to answer?
3. How did you start using metabolomics in your research?
4. What are the biggest problems you face with metabolomics research?
5. What is your primary method of discovering new methods and techniques to try as a clinician?

Team and infrastructure setup

6. Can you tell me a little about your team? When you need to run a metabolomics research experiments, who do you work with?
7. Who sets up the infrastructure for you to run your experiments?
8. Are there any technical shortcomings related to metabolomics that you need to overcome whether that be end user reporting or running experiments?

7.2. Moderator Guide Round 1

Hi,

Thank you so much in participating in this usability test of the new PhenoMeNal prototype. PhenoMeNal are tasked with setting up e-Infrastructure for researchers such as yourself. They are developing a prototype to enable this and have asked me to conduct some research to understand whether it is fit for purpose?

Today I will ask you to complete a couple of tasks on the prototype. The aim of the test is to determine whether the prototype is fit for purpose. You are not being tested, you are in fact doing the testing.

I will be your facilitator today. I will give you some tasks to do. While you perform these tasks it would be very helpful if you can think out loud. I do not work for PhenoMeNal and so feel free to be as frank as possible. As a facilitator I will not be able to guide you or give you hints. The prototype is very much in the early stages and our intention is to determine whether the functionality is easy to use. Some areas might not work as expected, let me know when you get stuck and we can move onto the next task.

I would like to record this session via screen/video recording to aid me in my analysis. All reporting will be anonymised, so for example you will be referred to as Test Participant 1. Will this be ok? [Get permission for recording]

Before we get started I would like to ask you a few questions?

Research Questions

1. Can you tell me what your job title is and also what you do?
2. Do you perform any metabolomic data analysis? If so, what are the problems you have had in the past?
3. Have you used any sort of cloud or virtual software infrastructure in the past and for what purpose?
4. In your view what are the most pressing problems in Metabolomics research?

Thanks for answering these questions? I would like to give you a few tasks to do with the prototype. I have sent you the link via the chat window?

Task 1: First impressions

This is the home page of the Gateway. Please don't click on anything yet? Can you tell me what you think this is about?

Start: Home Page

End: Home Page

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?

Task 2: Browse App Hub

Let us imagine that you are running a metabolomics experiment that requires lots of data processing? Can you find a way to see what tools are on offer through this Gateway?

Start: Home Page
End: App Hub Browse

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?
Probe 2: What do you think the panel on the left does?
Probe 3: If you click on two items from different sections what do you think will happen to your results?

Task 3: Find App

Say you are interested in a Galaxy workflow tool for metabolomics data processing? Can you see a way to view one?

Start: App Hub Browse
End: App Page

Probe 1: What do you think will happen if you click on the button “Deploy App on VRE”?
Probe 2: Can you see a way to deploy this application locally to your computer?

Task 4: Vi Research Environment

Can you find a way to find more information on the Cloud Research Environment?

Start: App Page
End: Virtual Research Environment Page

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?
Probe 2: Can you tell me in your own words what you think it is?

Task 5: Setup VRE

Let’s imagine that you are running a complex research project with lots of computing required? You would like to run your analysis using the VRE? Can you show me how you would set this up using this prototype?

Start: VRE Page
End: Successful setup of VRE

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?
Probe 2: What would you expect to find under the [Advanced] setup?
Probe 3: What sort of access would you like to your VRE?

Task 6: Find your VRE (Optional)

Let’s imagine you come back to this page and you are logged in. You want to find your VRE? Where would you go?

Start: Home Page
End: Profile VRE pages

Probe 1: What is your first instinct?

Probe 2: What do you think about the graphs?

In summary, what did you like or dislike about the prototype?

Well that is all I have for you today. Thank you so much for your time. We really do appreciate it and your comments will be very valuable in developing this tool further.

7.3. Moderator Guide Round 2

Hi,

Thank you so much in participating in this usability test of the new PhenoMeNal prototype. PhenoMeNal are tasked with setting up e-Infrastructure for researchers such as yourself. They are developing a prototype to enable this and have asked me to conduct some research to understand whether it is fit for purpose?

Today I will ask you to complete a couple of tasks on the prototype. The aim of the test is to determine whether the prototype is fit for purpose. You are not being tested, you are in fact doing the testing.

I will be your facilitator today. I will give you some tasks to do. While you perform these tasks it would be very helpful if you can think out loud. I do not work for PhenoMeNal and so feel free to be as frank as possible. As a facilitator I will not be able to guide you or give you hints. The prototype is very much in the early stages and our intention is to determine whether the functionality is easy to use. Some areas might not work as expected, let me know when you get stuck and we can move onto the next task.

I would like to record this session via screen/video recording to aid me in my analysis. All reporting will be anonymised, so for example you will be referred to as Test Participant 1. Will this be ok?
[Get permission for recording]

Before we get started I would like to ask you a few questions?

Research Questions

1. Can you tell me what your job title is and also what you do?
2. Do you perform any metabolomic data analysis? If so, what are the problems you have had in the past?
3. Have you used any sort of cloud or virtual software infrastructure in the past and for what purpose?
4. In your view what are the most pressing problems in Metabolomics research?

Thanks for answering these questions? I would like to give you a few tasks to do with the prototype. I have sent you the link via the chat window?

Task 1: First impressions

This is the home page of the Gateway. Please don't click on anything yet? Can you tell me what you think this is about?

Start: Home Page

End: Home Page

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?

Probe 2: What do you think is a Cloud Research Environment? What do you think is a better word for it: Virtual Research Environment or Cloud Research Environment.

Task 2: Browse App Hub

Let us imagine that you are running a metabolomics experiment that requires lots of data processing? Can you find a way to see what tools are on offer through this Portal?

Start: Home Page

End: App Hub Browse

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?

Probe 2: What do you think the panel on the left does?

Probe 3: If you click on two items from different sections what do you think will happen to your results?

Task 3: Find App

Say you are metabolomics data processing? Can you see a way to view one?

Start: App Hub Browse

End: App Page

Probe 1: What do you think will happen if you click on the button “Deploy App on CRE”?

Probe 2: Can you see a way to deploy this application locally to your computer?

Task 4: Cloud Research Environment

Can you find a way to find more information on the Cloud Research Environment?

Start: App Page

End: Virtual Research Environment Page

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?

Probe 2: Can you tell me in your own words what you think it is?

Task 5: Setup CRE

Let’s imagine that you are running a complex research project with lots of computing required? You would like to run your analysis using the CRE? Can you show me how you would set this up using this prototype?

Start: CRE Page

End: Successful setup of CRE

Probe 1: What are you thinking now?

Probe 2: What would you expect to find under the [Advanced] setup?

Probe 3: What sort of access would you like to your CRE?

Task 6: Local Installation

If you wanted to run this CRE on your own laptop how do you think you would find the information to do it?

Start: Home Page
End: Local CRE pages

Probe 1: What is your first instinct?

In summary, what did you like or dislike about the prototype?

Well that is all I have for you today. Thank you so much for your time. We really do appreciate it and your comments will be very valuable in developing this tool further.

7.4. PDF with annotations

Below are public links to the final, partly clickable, version of the wireframe mock-ups in PDF format, with comments. This document is 94 pages, hence it's not suitable to include directly into this document.

1. [PDF with annotations](#)
2. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BzjWaXXbS5X2VWZxVUg0U181dDg/view>